

GREEN PURCHASE BEHAVIOR: KEY FACTORS DRIVING ECO-FRIENDLY CONSUMER CHOICES FOR ENHANCED SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This study is about factors driving green purchase behavior in Karachi, considering ecological consciousness, WTP, skepticism, social influence, and consumer behavior intentions. From this, 203 respondents were drawn for the study, out of which the male participants accounted for 55.7% of the total sample, and 89.7% belonged to the age bracket of 25-35 years. The regression analysis of ECCB, WTP, and skepticism significantly impacts GPI. Still, social influence does not have significant effects on green purchase intention. The regression model adjusts the R-squared on prediction for GPI to be 0.732. It shows high reliability when explaining the green purchase intention. More importantly, GPI has a positive effect on GPB. In the case of this, the adjusted R-squared is 0.442. The study's outcome suggests that high ecological consciousness and price congruence with consumer expectations must exist to induce green purchases. Overpricing based on environmental benefits limits marketers' market access. Future studies need to use diverse demographic factors and a more significant population than the convenience sample used in the current study.

Keywords: Green purchase behavior (GPB), green purchase intention (GPI), ecological conscious consumer behavior (ECCB), willingness to pay (WTP), skepticism, social influence, sustainable consumption, sustainability, environmental marketing, and green products.

INTRODUCTION

This awareness of environmental issues and urgency built up over time to be placed against the need to face climate change has caused huge shifts in consumer behavior, more fundamentally in how people decide to buy things. For the last few decades, "green consumerism" has become one of the major pushes in the market; an increasingly larger proportion of the population feels concerned about sustainability and ethical production and the ecological implications behind each purchase. Green products, intended to cause the least harm in their entire lifecycle, are no longer an

inspirational niche offering but a major focus for firms in all sectors (Tripathi & Singh, 2016). Reforming the consumer markets fosters a much more expansive re-examination of corporate strategies, marketing techniques, and product development.

Green consumer behavior, therefore, is the inclination toward buying environmental goods and services perceived to be environmentally friendly or sustainable. Factors that affect green consumer behavior are ecological consciousness, willingness to pay premiums for sustainable products, and

skepticism about companies' claims regarding their environmental concern. This knowledge is important for scholars and marketers who must communicate with eco-friendly customers effectively. Researchers like Lokhande (2024) even request more research on this subject, primarily on how individual-level variables influence consumer purchase decisions, specifically regarding ecological awareness, social influence, and credibility of sustainability claims.

In addition to all these changes, sustainability has also increased interest in "greenwashing," the practice of making false claims about the benefits of a product for the environment to benefit from the growing demand for green products (Delmas & Burbano, 2011). Consumer skepticism becomes even more critical in shaping attitudes toward green products. Besides, consumers are more likely to claim skepticism concerning the authenticity of green branding, reducing their engagement in green purchasing behavior (Chan, 2000). To that extent, marketers and policymakers must discover how skepticism influences other factors of green behavior, like ecological consciousness and willingness to pay.

Demographic variables, such as age, gender, and income, have also been hot topics of interest in many studies on consumer behavior, including research on green consumerism. For instance, for some reason or other, Millennials and Gen Z have been considered the younger generations that are more pro-green buying than other generations, supposedly because of their heightened consciousness about the climate crisis and increasingly poor environmental outlook (Lokhande, 2024). The role of gender differences is also encompassed; some studies depict that, for example, women are more concerned about the environmental impact if a buying decision is made (Schlegelmilch et al., 1996). These demographic variables are rarely generalizable, and their effect on green purchasing may vary from culture to culture and product to product.

This research incorporates the drivers of green purchase behavior and reviews the

relationships between them. Four key variables are surveyed: ecological consciousness, willingness to pay, consumer skepticism, and green purchase intention. Ecological consciousness is people's awareness and concern about environmental matters and their preparedness to act to minimize their ecological footprint. The willingness to pay measures the willingness of a consumer to pay a premium for products with some observable environmental qualities. Distrust is the extent consumers believe the companies' claims are untrue. Lastly, green purchase intention refers to an individual's disposition to purchase green products in the future.

The study also tries to examine whether social influence can play a part in developing the behavior of a green consumer. Social influence is the influence that other people's opinions and actions exert on a person's purchase decisions, which becomes remarkably salient in green consumerism. As correctly pointed out, referring to Cialdini (2009), social norms and peer behaviors can strongly influence consumer attitudes and actions. Social influence has been cited as a major driver for sustainable behavior, given the increased knowledge about the environment, which has become more significant among youths owing to peer influence and information through social media (O'Loughlin et al., 2023).

Consumer Conduct in Green Buying Behavior is predicated on theoretical frameworks, including the Theory of Planned Behavior by Ajzen (1991). Thus, to TPB, behavior is determined by the individual through attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. To green consumerism, these elements form attitudes toward environmental sustainability and perceived social norms relating to eco-friendly purchases regarding how difficult or easy such purchases are likely to be. This conceptual model has been applied to a large body of research on sustainable consumption and has provided important insights regarding psychological and social antecedents of environmentally friendly consumer behavior (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006).

Besides individual-level antecedents, external antecedents include product features and communication messages that change consumer decisions. Earlier literature has been regarded as needing openness in communicating the values related to green products. With proper knowledge of a product's green advantages, consumers will likely exhibit pro-environmental purchasing behavior (Ali & Anwar, 2021). Ambiguous and inconsistent claims of sustainability only confuse the customers. Thus, the trust and chances of purchasing green drift down the drain (Rahman & Luomala, 2021).

This study is important in its contribution to academic literature and practical marketing strategies. It theoretically ties in with studies conducted looking at the relationship of ecological consciousness with skepticism and willingness to pay with the intention of green purchase. It brings in the factors of social influence that have yet to be much explored in the context of green consumerism. From a more practical point of view, such insights help businesses and policymakers design the right strategy for sustainable consumption. Furthermore, understanding the factors of green purchase behavior also enables firms to design marketing campaigns and product offerings and pursue sustainability initiatives in line with the requirements of such eco-conscious consumers.

The present research contributes to the emerging body of literature about green consumerism by focusing on a diverse sample of consumers across different age groups, employment statuses, and income levels. In this context, companies that wish to target different markets appropriately in an increasingly mainstream green consumerism must understand consumer behavior in the context of various demographic segments. The paper constructs a broader understanding of these green consumers and how they buy those products by examining income, education, and occupation concerning ecological consciousness and purchasing intentions. The following part of the paper forms the methodology of conducting the study and the design of the survey instrument, the

sampling strategy, and the statistical approaches applied to present the analysis results. It has been selected so that the several factors of influence on green consumer behaviors are considered holistically, making the results valid and generalizable. We hope this study contributes to our better understanding of the dynamics of sustainable consumption and derives actionable insights for the business world in meaningful interaction with conscious consumers.

1.1 Problem Statement

Green purchasing and eco-innovation are important factors in developing an eco-friendly environment. Eco-innovation centers on consolidating natural supportability at each progression of the formation of possessions and facilities, which prompts limiting asset utilization and "offers" reasonable advantage. GPB describes the buying behavior of those commodities that are friendly to the environment and limits those commodities that create hazards for the environment and any other living. GPB also shows responsible decision-making behavior, measured by SRB (Socially Responsible Behavior). SCB (Social Capable Buyer), the green customer, "considers the general population results of own private utilization for examples and endeavors to utilize own acquiring capacity to achieve social reorganization.

Eco-dependable buying is very important and should be purchased like spontaneous buying, which can create impact. Grunert and Juhl (1995) revealed that 40 percent of households were accountable for environmental harm. This percentage can be reduced through awareness, self-contribution, and continuous effort to save environmental damage by purchasing green products. Green purchasing and eco-innovation are important factors in developing an eco-friendly environment. Eco-innovation centres on consolidating natural supportability at each progression of the formation of possessions and facilities, which prompts limiting asset utilization and "offers" reasonable advantage. However, despite such efforts, consumer adoption of

green products and services remains limited, suggesting significant barriers and challenges to driving widespread green purchase behavior (Nguyen & Hoang, 2023; Liao et al., 2020; Tsai & Liao, 2016).

GPB describes the buying behavior of those commodities that are friendly to the environment and limits those commodities that create hazards for the environment and any other living. GPB also shows responsible decision-making behavior, measured by SRB (Socially Responsible Behavior). Therefore, understanding the factors influencing green purchase behavior is crucial, as it can help identify barriers and unlock opportunities to promote sustainable consumption (Singh et al., 2023; Nguyen & Hoang, 2023; Tsai & Liao, 2016).

SCB (Social Capable Buyer), the green customer, "considers the general population results of own private utilization for examples and endeavors to utilize own acquiring capacity to achieve social reorganization. A vital component in shaping green purchase behavior is the extent to which consumers are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products with a lower environmental impact, as this reflects the value they place on environmental attributes when making purchasing decisions. Eco-dependable buying is very important and should be purchased like spontaneous buying, which can create impact. Grunert and Juhl (1995) revealed that 40 percent of households were accountable for environmental harm. This percentage can be reduced through awareness, self-contribution, and continuous effort to save environmental damage by purchasing green products. This research aims to examine the key individual-level determinants that shape green purchase behavior among consumers in Karachi, Pakistan, focusing on ecological consciousness, willingness to pay, skepticism towards sustainability claims, and social influence.

1.2 Significance of the Study

One of the studies from India carries a special background, showing research significance for many reasons. ESB

(Environmentally sensitive behavior) includes a person's activities to confine contrary activities that may positively impact the environment. This can be possible by diminishing resources and energy usage, utilizing hostile to lethal materials, or controlling wastage. Also, some models, like the Norm Activation Model and Value-Belief-Norm, are the theoretical models' researchers had designed to estimate GPB (Stern et al., 1999). Whoever reviews the SI (Self-interested behavior) model prefers to use coherent result models like TPB (Ajzen, 1991). Societies have discovered that SI impacts GBB (Green Buying Behavior), and ecological norms influence PD (Purchase Decisions) (Lee, 2009; Chan, 2001). Researchers also concluded that everyday life, principles, and culture impact GPB (Kim & Chung, 2011; Jansson et al., 2010).

1.3 Scope of the Study

In many ways, it is important to show concern about the consequences of GBS (Green Buying Strategy). Due to globalization, competition among industries has significantly increased, creating the demand for the safety issue of the environment. The emphasis on environmentalism is a separating factor in setting up a decent arrangement of customers. To address such difficulties, this examination centers around the changing and developing parts of purchaser buy conduct and sets certain systems to the extent of green purchasing methodology. This paper examines where a decent measure of exertion has been spent to break down the key determinants of buyer basic leadership conduct and demeanors that infer such technique. This exploration can be recognized as a key for organizations that intend to create a green buying strategy, considering the necessities and desires of the neighborhood. It is noted that SI, WTP, and other factors play a prominent role in the value creation of local consumers within the market regarding GBB and ECCB.

2. Literature Review

Green purchasing behavior, or the penchant among consumers for products labeled as

environmentally friendly, has been noted to shift drastically in the last decade as environmentalism and concerns over climate change gain prominence. Determinants of green purchasing behavior tend to be demographic characteristics, motivational drivers, external influences, education, and policy. A few demographic factors are age, gender, income, and education level, all of which affect consumers' green purchases. For example, it has been established in many studies that younger populations, such as millennials and Generation Z, have greater environmental awareness and a higher likelihood of engaging in green consumption (Ghaffar & Islam, 2024; Zhao et al., 2020). However, despite their claimed environmental concerns, younger consumers may be constrained by some of these factors to be more price-sensitive and have a lower income or a weak actual purchasing power for sustainable products (Reisch et al., 2020). Gender also plays an incremental role in the variations of green purchase behavior. Studies repeatedly prove that women are more likely to act in sustainable consumption more often than their male counterparts, primarily because of stronger environmental values and social responsibility (Essiz et al., 2023). Moreover, consumers with a higher income and education are more prone to engaging in green purchases because they are financially and literarily well-off enough to be worth the premium of being environmentally friendly (Ghaffar, A., & Islam, 2024). Education makes them aware of the environmental impact, motivating consumers to choose eco-friendly (Al-Nuaimi & Al-Ghamdi, 2022). Motivational factors for purchasing green can be broadly categorized into intrinsic and extrinsic factors, critical indicators for determining consumer decisions. Those intrinsic factors, namely environmental values, ethical concerns, and social responsibilities are the principal motivational stimuli that result in consumers behaving greenly. For example, consumers guided by ethical values are more likely to show interest in purchasing green as a matter of moral obligation and thus sustainable consumption as living up to personal

conviction (Rana & Solaiman, 2023; Mastria et al., 2023). Extrinsic factors include price, convenience, and efficiency that guide the practical decision-making of consumers. Consumers today are price-sensitive, and the environment is sacrificed if these green products come at a cost, or in other words, have no near-term value for consumers (Mastria et al., 2023). Quality of perception and product differentiation also affect the gap between expressed environmental concern and actual green purchasing; in other words, the sustainable product must convey value for stable purchasing to be sustained (Zhao et al., 2020). Social influence determines green purchase intentions since social norms and peer behaviors influence most consumers. Increased prevalence of sustainable behavior among their social circles may motivate people to create similar patterns, especially with how easy it is for these green products and sustainable lifestyle choices to be shared through social media and digitalization (Zafar et al., 2021; Shang & Wu, 2022).

Other broad external forces determine consumer choices towards environmentally friendly products. A good example is marketing. Many strategies are implemented, such as what the government decides and the role played by social media. Marketing is one of the primary channels through which brands aim to target environment-conscious consumers. In a real sense, consumers cannot understand or rely on the labels. This causes them not to be convinced of green claims, and thus, transparency is needed (Ghaffar & Islam, 2024). Indeed, transparent green marketing builds chances to decline consumer distrust; hence, it is important for firms interested in reaching environmentally conscious consumers (Essiz et al., 2023). Governmental policies and incentives also facilitate green buying. Tax incentives, subsidy policies, and eco-label regulation enhance consumer attitudes towards a greener attitude and move the consumer to greater eco-friendly buying (Rana & Solaiman, 2023). Adding to consumers' awareness and responsibility, regulations that enforce corporate environmental transparency have enhanced

their sustainable purchasing behavior (Zhao et al., 2020). Social media and online communities have become powerful mediums for spreading awareness about sustainable products. Social media fosters consumers discussing green products or even sharing with others the peer reviews they receive, which significantly influences the purchase intention. For example, the information exchange on these platforms maintains green behavior with maximum reinforcement from consumers with high social status and peer validation in high esteem (Shang & Wu, 2022).

Education and awareness are two very crucial parts of inciting green purchasing behavior. Studies establish that consumers possessing formal environmental education have a higher chance of such sustainable conduct since they are aware of the effects of their choice (Al-Nuaimi & Al-Ghamdi, 2022). Educating consumers on the benefits of green products and the wider impacts of climate change fosters responsible consumption. It underscores the role of educative interventions in developing sustainable behavior (Mastria et al., 2023). CSR initiatives also firm up green purchasing so consumer trust and loyalty grow with CSR. Businesses that employ CSR and reveal true sustainability in their operations increase the likelihood of attracting green consumers. CSR efforts attract environmentally sensitive consumers and may lead to more loyalty and repeat consumer buying (Essiz et al., 2023).

The overarching theme that stitches together consumer motivations, demographic influences, policy initiatives, and educational efforts involves sustainability. In simple terms, sustainability is satisfying existing needs without affecting future resources. In recent years, sustainability has influenced consumer behavior and corporate practices (Concari et al., 2020). Consumers with long-term environmental

consequences tend to opt for sustainable alternatives. Their values are the driving force behind such purchases. Companies adopting transparent and authentic sustainability practices build consumer trust and brand loyalty that can compensate for price sensitivity amongst consumers and even encourage a willingness to pay (Kim et al., 2024). Government incentives, social influence, and easy access to sources of information enhance the development of a sustainability culture that turns green purchases into everyday behaviors for contemporary consumers (Singh et al., 2023). The literature depicts that a complex mix of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, demographics, policy frameworks, and educational awareness influences green purchasing behavior. Personal values, social influence, and the tangible benefits of green products drive consumers. Demographic factors, such as age, gender, income, and education, affect the tendency to buy sustainable products. Besides, governmental policies, social networking sites, and CSR activities form additional factors that encourage green purchasing. Considering all these variables allows companies and policymakers to better respond to consumers' demands toward sustainability, thus leading to more environmentally friendly consumption practices.

2.1 Hypothesis

H1: Willing to pay (WTP) has a significant impact on GPI.

H2: Ecology conscious consumer behavior (ECCB) has a significant impact on GPI.

H3: Skepticism (SKEP) has a significant impact on GPI.

H4: Social influence (SI) has a significant impact on GPI.

H5: Green Purchase Intension (GPI) has a significant impact on GPB.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The hypotheses in this GPB research study fit well with some of the most important constructs identified in recent literature. The first is the conceptualization of Willingness to Pay, or to what extent consumers are willing to pay a premium for sustainable products, often described as a predictor of GPI. Consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products are, therefore, more committed to green purchases and ready to accept the cost of such a decision as part of an investment in preserving the environment; many comments on it being a necessary investment for environmental conservation (Pham et al., 2023; Chung & Cho, 2023). Similarly, Ecologically Conscious Consumer Behavior (ECCB), consumers' attention to the ecological impacts of their actions, is heavily found to influence the GPI positively as ecological activists prefer sustainable purchases. The other stream of literature that fits into this consideration is the impact of Skepticism (SKEP) towards green claims, as it is quite well-backed through research showing that in cases where consumers have doubts about the authenticity of green marketing, their purchasing intentions might be negatively affected (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2021; Reisch et al., 2020). On the other hand, SI, or the impact of peer or social community engagement in sustainable behavior, has persistently been associated with enhanced GPI, even concerning the expansion of social media platforms through

which such sustainable behaviors are publicly displayed but rather promoted (Suki, N. M., & Suki, 2019).

Finally, the transition from GPI to GPB is a very important domain because, in many places, intention does not necessarily lead to action. Recent studies reveal that although GPI is a powerful predictor of GPB, the values surrounding access to the product and affordability of products, apart from the social norms, affect these values (Farzana et al., 2024). These research hypotheses, therefore, contextualize the study within a more holistic scope of understanding the beliefs of the individual, social dynamics, and behavioral intentions toward sustainable consumer behavior.

3. Methodology

The unit of analysis for my project is to identify consumers. This research is explanatory. In this research, a deductive approach has been taken. Data collection is based on primary data through a quantitative method in which a survey questionnaire is taken.

3.1 Sampling Size

Data is collected through a convenient sample technique. The respondents are students, influencers, and professionals from different industries. The sample size used for analysis is approximately 203 respondents. Researchers observed that young customers are more enthusiastic about providing fresh

ideas (Ottman et al., 2006). Young people are a part of this sample size because they have been known to show their environmental concern and responsibility toward ecology and its protection. In this research, the convenience sampling technique has been utilized to acquire some "quick" data to get a "feel" for the phenomenon or variable of interest. In this research, the multiple linear regression technique has been used.

3.2 Ethical Consideration

Gray (2004) identifies the major issues that may arise in the initial phase of any research. In any case, the research analyst intentionally or un-deliberately constrains the group of respondents in the research. The central ethics are that the respondents should be particularly instructed about the explanation behind the investigation. Furthermore, the examiner must experience the related principles to prepare his/her respondent for the idea behind his/her research.

- The respondents should understand the purpose and goals of the study.
- This research identified no suspicious or harmful effects to the respondents.
- No other supporters back this research.
- Each respondent's participation took 5 to 10 minutes.
- Participation is voluntary for this research.
- Respondents should realize that their involvement is highly encouraged and beneficial to the research.
- The data should be private, and it ought to be utilized only for scholarly purposes.
- At the end stage, no sound or visual promotions should be utilized to gather information.

4. Data and Analysis

Table 1 summarizes the respondent's gender. The final sample contains 203 respondents, of which 113 are male, which is 55.7% of the total respondents, and 90 are females, which carries 44.3% of the total respondents.

Table-1
Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	113	55.7	55.7	55.7
	Female	90	44.3	44.3	100.0
	Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 summarizes the demographic profile of the respondents. The final sample consists of 203, ages 25-23, and 182, which carries 89.7% of the total respondents; 36-45 15,

which carries 7.4% of the total respondents; and 46-55 6, which carries 3% of the total respondents.

Table-2
Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	25 till 35	182	89.7	89.7	89.7
	36 till 45	15	7.4	7.4	97.0
	46 till 55	6	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 summarizes the respondent's employment status. The final sample size contains 203 respondents, of which 71 are Executive, which carries 35% of the total respondents; 88 belong to Management,

which carries 43.3% of total respondents; and 44 are Self Employed, which carries 21.7% of the total respondents.

Table-3

Employment Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Executive	71	35.0	35.0	35.0
Management	88	43.3	43.3	78.3
Self Employed	44	21.7	21.7	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Cronbach Test

Cronbach tests are applied to check the consistency of the items in this research. This research carries six variables. Green purchase behavior has four items that carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.808; Skepticism has four items that carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.797; willingness to pay has five items that

carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.893; Green purchase intention has eight items that carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.940, Ecology Conscious consumer behavior has nine items which carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.932, Social Influence has three items which carry Cronbach's Alpha 0.743.

Case Processing Summary

	N	%
Cases Valid	203	100.0
Excluded ^a	0	.0
Total	203	100.0

Table-4: Green Purchase Behavior

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.808	4

Table-5: Skepticism

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.797	4

Table-6

Willingness to pay

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.893	5

Table-7

Green Purchase Intension

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.940	8

Table-8

Ecology Conscious Consumer Behavior

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.932	9

Table-9
Social Influence

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.743	3

Hypothesis Testing

In this research, linear regression analysis is performed to test the hypothesis in two parts. In the first part, liner regression is applied with four independent variables (WTP, SKIP, SI, and ECCB) and one dependent variable (GPI), and in the second part, liner regression is applied with one independent variable (GPI) and dependent variable (GPB).

Part One

The result suggested the reliability of the model by showing a 0.732 Adjusted R Square value, which is considerable; thus, our model was accepted. Moreover, our research shows that SKEP has a 0.001 sig value, WTP has a 0.000 sig value, ECCB has a 0.000 sig value, and SI has a 0.452 sig value, which means that SKI, WTP, ECCB have a significant impact on GPI and SI do not have a significant impact on GPI.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.863 ^a	.745	.732	.52723		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Influence, Skepticism, Ecological Conscious Consumer Behavior, Willingness to pay						
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.861	4	16.215	58.335	.000 ^a
	Residual	22.237	80	.278		
	Total	87.099	84			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Influence, Skepticism, Ecological Conscious Consumer Behavior, Willingness to pay						
b. Dependent Variable: Green purchase intention						

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.863 ^a	.745	.732	.52723

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.300	.234		1.282	.201	-.162	.762
	Skepticism	.210	.060	.185	3.506	.001	.092	.328
	Willingness to pay	.276	.062	.286	4.474	.000	.155	.398
	Ecological Conscious Consumer Behavior	.462	.069	.446	6.728	.000	.327	.598
	Social Influence	.033	.043	.033	.754	.452	-.053	.118

a. Dependent Variable: Green purchase intention

Part two

The result suggested the reliability of the model by showing a 0.442 Adjusted R Square value, which is considerable; thus,

our model was accepted. Moreover, our research shows that GPI has a 0.000 sig value, which means GPI significantly impacts GPB.

Regression

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.670 ^a	.448	.442	.76726

a. Predictors: (Constant), Green purchase intention

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	39.709	1	39.709	67.454	.000 ^a	
	Residual	48.860	83	.589			
	Total	88.569	84				

a. Predictors: (Constant), Green purchase intention

b. Dependent Variable: Green Purchase Behaviour

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.713	.277		2.570	.012		
	Green purchase intention	.675	.082	.670	8.213	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Green Purchase Behaviour

5. Discussion of Findings

This study aims to understand the factors influencing GPB and the variables that may impact SKEP, WTP, ECCB, and SI. Insights are derived from analyses of how these factors might influence consumer intentions and behaviors regarding environmentally friendly products. The sample for this study consisted of 203 respondents with a gender split, as shown in Table 1: males at 55.7% and females at 44.3%. In many previous studies, differences are noted based on gender when the differences made in purchasing behavior related to eco-friendliness. This is often higher among males than females regarding sustainable consumption (Zander, K., & Hamm, 2010). Most of the respondents, 89.7%, fall in the category of 25-35 years old, a pattern very commonly noticed in recent studies wherein the younger generations are more likely to exhibit green purchasing behavior due to increased awareness of the environment. Employment status is reported by 43.3% in managerial positions, 35% in executive or

management positions, and 21.7% as self-employed (Table 3), indicating an overall professional profile sample, which may justify the adoption of the decisions related to purchase according to income level or from ecological issues.

Cronbach's Alpha values for all variables in the study showed that this has taken place satisfactorily in terms of internal consistency. For Green Purchase Behavior (GPB), the alpha is 0.808; Skepticism (SKEP) equaled 0.797, and Willingness to Pay (WTP) equaled 0.893, with an identification of a good level of reliability across constructs (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). These results, therefore, suggest that each construct is measured using relatively stable and consistent items, confirming the instrument's validity.

Two linear regression models are used to test hypotheses. In the first model, four independent variables, SKEP, WTP, ECCB, and SI, are tested against Green Purchase Intention (GPI). The outcomes show that SKEP, WTP, and ECCB significantly

positively affect GPI, as their p-values are less than 0.05; however, Social Influence is statistically insignificant toward GPI (Table 5). However, this is opposite from what has recently been established by the study's findings, suggesting that consumer attitudes toward sustainability are much more influenced by personal values and financial willingness rather than social forces (Liaquat et al., 2022). The Adjusted R Square value of 0.732 indicates that these four variables jointly explain a very considerable proportion of variance for the GPI, thus emphasizing model robustness.

In the second regression model, Green Purchase Intention is the measure that could predict Green Purchase Behavior significantly, as shown in Table 9 with a p-value of 0.000. This justifies the hypothesis that consumer intentions toward buying a greener product predict their eventual behavior, which finds consistency with previous research pointing toward the intention-behavior gap prevailing in sustainable consumption, as identified by Vermeir, I., & Verbeke, (2006). The Adjusted R Square value is 0.442, which further suggests that GPI explains only 44.2% of the variance in GPB and further establishes the fact that though intention is an important determinant of behavior, other factors also determine purchase behavior.

Marketers can enhance consumer purchase intention by reducing skepticism and enhancing the perceived ecological benefits of green products. The important role of WTP and ECCB further suggests that consumers' willingness to pay more for environment-friendly products and their ecological awareness play a pivotal role in green purchasing behavior (Wang et al., 2021; Barbu et al., 2022). However, this study also fails to achieve a significant impact of SI, which may, in turn, suggest that environmental concerns are more personal and intrinsic rather than socially driven in the context of green purchasing (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006).

Moreover, the survey's population is primarily below age 45 and has regular employment. This may not represent the greater population, limiting how much one

can generalize conclusions from this survey regarding other ages or socio-economic backgrounds. Future work will likely deepen our knowledge about the factors underlying green purchasing behavior by investigating how age, educational level, and cultural factors intersect (Pasdiora et al., 2020).

The results of this study provide fertile ground for the emerging body of literature on green consumer behavior. Despite the strong influence of skepticism, willingness to pay, and ecological consciousness on purchase intentions, Social Influence is relatively ineffectual. This finds some reflection in how the apparent preservation of inner consumer factors- in this case, personal values and beliefs- are even stronger than outer factors, such as social influence. It benefits marketers and policymakers by defining proper strategies to encourage green consumption, focusing on consumer awareness, and alleviating consumers' skepticism about ecological products.

6. Conclusion

Ecologically conscious consumer behavior has a more positive influence on green purchase behavior than green purchase intention. This insight allows the marketer to target their positioning and promotional strategies better so that the environmental and social benefits resonate with customers. A powerful green marketing approach encourages companies to adopt green management and transform all their marketing strategies, ensuring their considerations go beyond financial impact and into the social and ecological dimensions. This study demonstrates the growing consistency of beliefs and practices among consumers regarding their purchasing behavior, which provides new knowledge for marketers in proactive strategy building. The latter must be designed to demonstrate the benefits of the environment and the impact the product can have on the environment rather than educating consumers regarding environmental issues.

Additionally, producers should not hype products too much as "green" products or charge excessive premiums. Overhyping or high premiums may restrict the market to

niche markets alone and make it less conceivable for mass adoption. Therefore, such green practices must become part of the corporate culture and ethics, ensuring a safe environment for products yet affordable to all customers. The retail giant should also provide a range of products for the different green products available on the market so that consumers can make informed decisions for better environmental protection.

This research also critically examines the influence of skepticism on GPB. There are thorough documents on what influences GPB, yet skepticism has not been adequately discussed. In sharp contrast, the observational findings suggest that consumer skepticism influenced GPB, although it was detrimental to EC and PCE. Of the two, however, PCE is much more positive than EC in its influence, which suggests that, in future research, these factors can be explored further using multi-method approaches and how varying consumer demographics may have a bearing on GPB is studied.

However, social influences-"exposure to environmental messages, authority figures, for example"-can play an important role in changing the behavior of a collectivist culture consumer. These can be further teased using frameworks like the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which can predict consumer choices, and which socio-demographic factors may influence green purchasing behavior. Using TPB, researchers look deeper into what psychological and social factors drive green purchasing behavior and develop effective interventions to change this behavior.

7. Limitations

In this research, a few limitations must be considered, specifically using a comfort test, which constrains its capability. The expansion can discourage a few respondents' contribution to self-reported measures to assess the variable of interest. A couple of focuses for future research headway are displayed: the clearer depiction of the green customer profiling, which impacts a correct division of clients with the ultimate objective of making green thing commitments

concerning the honest-to-goodness required. This research was specifically carried out in Karachi only, and the results cannot be generalized to the whole country, even though it is a worthy representative city. In this way, the investigations have a chance to gather test information from all over the nation, with the goal that the outcomes can be summed up the national dimension.

Green Buys conduct alludes to buying ecologically well-disposed items or manageable items that are 'recyclable' and 'advantageous' to nature and maintaining a strategic distance from such items that hurt the earth and society. Professionals and scholastics in the world need to take the perspective of the consistently expanding natural issues and receive practical improvement trials to limit the harmful impacts of impromptu advancement on states. Ecological advancement and green buying are indispensable segments of maintainable improvement. Earth touchy conduct includes a person's endeavors to restrict adverse activities that may harm the characteristics and physical condition.

This should be possible by diminishing asset and vitality use, utilizing hostile to poisonous materials, or diminishing waste creation. It is imperative to understand the significance of green purchasing procedures from numerous points of view. As there is an abnormal state of rivalry throughout the world because of globalization issues, there is a developing interest in the issues of environmentalism. In this sense, centering around environmentalism is a separating factor in setting up a decent arrangement of clients.

To address such difficulties, this examination centers around the changing and rising parts of purchase buy conduct and sets certain systems to the extent of the green purchasing procedure. In this examination, there are a few impediments to consider, specifically the utilization of comfort that constrains the capability of the ends, the expansion of the poll that may demoralize a few respondents' support, and the use of other measures to evaluate the variable of interest.

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